

Evaluation of Hidden Trends of Sugarcane Production in India through Innovative Trend Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Sugarcane is a prominent source of sugar and is recognized as one of the leading commercial crops globally because of its multi-utility and contribution to the ecological balance. The main aim of this study is to perform a statistical trend analysis to examine hidden trends in sugarcane production across 19 Indian states during 1981–2022.

Research Method: In this regard, a recently well-accepted advanced trend methodology, namely innovative trend analysis (ITA), is adopted with the motto to graphically visualize and classify internal complex trends at various clusters (i.e., low, medium, and high). These clusters are important for future studies on underproduction as low and overproduction as high. Furthermore, calculations of the average rate of change in trend slope provide valuable information regarding the overall trend of sugarcane production.

Findings: According to the study mentioned above, neither the APT in the medium cluster nor Himachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, and Mizoram in the low cluster showed any discernible trend. The remaining states exhibited either increasing or decreasing trends in the cluster. APT and Punjab did not show any significant trends over the period, and the remaining states followed increasing and decreasing trends. Moreover, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Karnataka exhibited strong positive growth rates, while Odisha, Rajasthan, and Assam demonstrated declining trends. The highlight of the analysis is that the ITA method explores extensive interpretations of trend detection of sugarcane production, and these cannot be evaluated by any other traditional methods.

Keywords: Hidden trends, India, Innovative trend analysis, Scatter plots, Sugarcane

1. INTRODUCTION

Sugarcane belonging to the *Gramineae* family is an extensively cultivated crop yield in India. Sugarcane is a natural source of vital nutrients, including potassium, magnesium, calcium, amino acids, and several vitamins. It is the main source of raw materials for the production of sugar and is primarily used for the preparation of jaggery, sugar, ethanol, and various by-products. Beyond sugar, it also contributes to the production of ethanol (biofuel), rum, other alcoholic beverages, animal feed, biogas, and molasses. Sugarcane emerged as the nation's most important commercial crop, and it plays a key role in industrial purposes, providing employment to lakhs of people directly and indirectly while also making a significant contribution to the growth of the economy. Over time, sugarcane spread along human migration routes to Asia and the Indian subcontinent, where it hybridised with wild sugarcane species, leading to the development of commercial varieties.

India is historically recognized as the birthplace of sugarcane and sugar. It is the world's second-largest producer of sugar, following Brazil. A significant portion of the agricultural workforce is engaged in sugarcane cultivation, harvesting, and related activities. The sugarcane industry faces multiple challenges, including climate change, unpredictable weather patterns, and water scarcity, all of which directly impact yield. These fluctuations in production, coupled with global market trends, lead to frequent variations in sugar prices. Additionally, limited mechanization and outdated techniques reduce efficiency and create imbalances in supply. Although demand for sugar remains steady, inconsistencies in production contribute to price volatility. Therefore, accurate forecasting of sugarcane output is essential for stabilizing prices and ensuring a reliable supply of bioethanol (Supriya, 2023).

To address these challenges, advancements in precision farming, drip irrigation, high-yield seed varieties, and improved harvesting techniques are being implemented. Additionally, the promotion of ethanol production from sugarcane has created new opportunities for sustainable energy and economic growth. With strategic planning, innovation, and government support, sugarcane will remain a cornerstone of India's agricultural and industrial sectors, contributing to economic stability, job creation, and renewable energy production. Notably, sugar prices are among the most volatile of all agricultural commodities globally (Elobeid and Beghin, 2006; Maitah and Smutka, 2019).

Singh *et al.* (2021a) investigated trends and identified change points in India's sugarcane production using well-established non-parametric methods, including Pettitt's test, the standard normal homogeneity test, and Buishand's range test. Arti and Rai (2017) investigated sugarcane cultivation trends in Uttar Pradesh by analyzing key factors such as

area, production, and yield using the compound annual growth rate (CAGR). Their study assessed variations in these parameters and provided valuable insights into the state's agricultural growth dynamics. Singh *et al.* (2021b) calculated spatial compound growth rates to analyze growth patterns and assessed instability in the area, production, and productivity of sugarcane in major sugarcane-producing states of India.

Several researchers have utilized ARIMA models to analyze and forecast sugarcane production trends in India. For example, Sanjeev *et al.* (2015) applied ARIMA models to examine sugarcane yield across districts in Haryana, demonstrating their effectiveness for short-term predictions. Similarly, Suresh and Priya (2011) used ARIMA models to forecast sugarcane area, production, and productivity in Tamil Nadu. Mishra *et al.* (2021) extended this approach by using ARIMA models to predict sugarcane production across multiple Indian states. These studies highlighted the model's reliability in agricultural forecasting.

Trend analysis is a statistical technique used to identify patterns, movements, or changes in data over time. The main feature of trend analysis is to examine the historical data to detect consistent tendencies, fluctuations, or emerging trends, which can be used for forecasting and decision-making. Trend analysis involves various statistical methodologies to detect tendencies in data over time. Parametric approaches, such as linear regression analysis, polynomial regression, and the ARIMA model. Non-parametric methods, including the Mann-Kendall test, the Theil-Sen estimator, Spearman's rho (SR) test, the modified Mann-Kendall test, and the ITA method, are more flexible and suitable for datasets with unknown or non-normal distributions (Gemmer *et al.*, 2011; Tabari *et al.*, 2011; Esterby, 2015; Yuefeng *et al.*, 2020; Kalpana *et al.*, 2020). These methods are expanded in agriculture, to study the trend patterns of crops production such as castor (Kalpana *et al.*, 2019), wheat (Kalpana and Kiran 2020), rice (Kalpana *et al.*, 2021), and food grains (Kalpana *et al.*, 2023) have also used trend analysis techniques.

Among these, the innovative trend analysis (ITA) method is an extended version of MK test and it is recently well accepted for detecting trend intensity in time series data, offering a graphical approach that facilitates intuitive analysis. Unlike traditional methods, ITA does not rely on statistical assumptions such as serial correlation, normality of distribution and data length. Sen (2017) enhanced the ITA method by introducing a calculation framework for deriving monotonic trends and conducting significance tests. ITA not only graphically visualises the trend but also estimates trend magnitude, similar to the Theil-Sen estimator. However, Theil-Sen remains a widely accepted method for quantifying trend magnitude, particularly for linear trends, whereas ITA is more flexible in detecting nonlinear patterns

(Junli *et al.*, 2018; Zhou *et al.*, 2018; Malik *et al.*, 2019; Ali *et al.*, 2019; Kuriqi *et al.*, 2020; Liaqat *et al.*, 2022). Studies comparing the ITA method with classical statistical approaches have demonstrated several advantages of ITA.

Several researchers have applied the ITA method to effectively perform the trend analysis in various fields. For example, Pastagia and Mehta (2022) analysed seasonal rainfall trends in the Rajsamand district of Rajasthan. Kalpana and Chesneau (2024) analysed CO₂ emissions patterns across various sectors like coal, oil, gas, and cement in India and China. Shah *et al.* (2022) studied the annual, seasonal, and extreme precipitation trends in Korea's Han River Basin. Yilinuer *et al.* (2020) studied monthly precipitation trends of three meteorological stations (Balykchy, Cholpon-Ata, and Kyzyl-Suu) around Lake Issyk-Kul. Kisi (2015) analyzed hidden trends in monthly pan evaporation data and determined that the ITA method was more effective than the SR and MK tests. Wu and Qian (2017) highlighted the advantages of the ITA method over linear regression and the MK test in trend detection. Dong *et al.* (2020) evaluated temperature trends at various clusters, such as low, median, and high-value groups, and observed that trends were raised in the high cluster.

In addition to that, Caloiero *et al.* (2018) studied seasonal rainfall patterns in southern Italy; Ay and Kisi (2015) studied trends of various regions in Turkey; Ishfaq *et al.* (2022) analysed the trends of climatic variables rainfall and temperature of the Jhelum Basin in the Kashmir Valley; Kenabatho (2025) studied rainfall trends in Botswana; Emmanuel *et al.* (2025) detected precipitation patterns in Nigeria; Wissanupong *et al.* (2024) studied trends of humidity and temperature; and Mohammed *et al.* (2022) detected rainfall trends in the Wadi Mina basin.

As of now, analysis of sugarcane production across India focused on forecasting it with ARIMA. In addition to that, growth rates and trend patterns were studied by CGR, exponential time series models and MK tests. Besides, the innovative trend analysis methodologies have not been applied to study the intensity of the trend for sugarcane production in India. Thus, evaluating the trend intensities of sugarcane production at different clusters (low, medium, and high) and calculating the trend change rate using the ITA approach are the primary concerns of the current work. The analysis helps to deeply understand how the various states are involved in the contribution of production in India.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sugarcane production data has been taken from the Reserve Bank of India. This study focuses on the yearly production data of sugarcane across 19 states in India for the period 1981–2022.

According to standard literature on trend methodologies (Sen, 2012), the innovative trend analysis (ITA) method is appropriate to find both monotonic and nonmonotonic trends. This technique enables a visual representation of data trends and also facilitates a clearer interpretation of trend behaviour overtime. ITA scatter plots have been specifically developed to uncover trends within complex datasets in both scientific and economic research. It does not satisfy any statistical assumptions such as autocorrelation or sample size (Elouissi *et al.*, 2016; Alashan, 2018). The methodology involves the following steps:

Step 1: Divide the dataset into two equal sub-series that represent the first half and the second half, then arrange the two halves individually in ascending order.

Step 2: The values from the first half are plotted on the x-axis while, the values from the second half are plotted on the y-axis. A 1:1 trendless line (i.e., a 45-degree diagonal) is drawn, representing a no trend (no change over time).

Step 3: Moreover, horizontal axis in the graph is segmented into three equal clusters (i.e., low, medium and high) based on percentiles (Dong *et al.*, 2020; Alashan, 2018). Through this classification, it is possible to study the deviations in different production groups such as low, medium and high, based on the data positions in scatter plot.

Step 4: The Control Limits (CL) for the plot are defined as $y_1 \pm 0.05(\bar{y}_1)$ at 95% confidence.

Suppose the points lying above the 1:1 line are indicating an increasing trend, while the points lying below the 1:1 line indicate a decreasing trend. Points clustering along the diagonal suggest no trend. The points lying on one side of the 450 trendless line are known as a monotonic trend. If fluctuations occur over time, know it as a non-monotonic trend. Furthermore, a trend is considered significant if any or all of the data points are outside the control limits. Otherwise, no significant trend. The above procedure can reveal only the nature of the trend and the mathematical expression of trend slop is formulated by the extension work of ITA method, it was introduced by Sen (2017) is given below:

$$S = \frac{2(\bar{y}_2 - \bar{y}_1)}{n}$$

Where n is the number of observations on each half, \bar{y}_1 and \bar{y}_2 represent the mean of the first and second halves of the data respectively. A positive value of S specifies an upward trend, while a negative value specifies a downward trend. The confidence limits of the trend slope follow a standard normal probability density function as follows:

$$CL_{(1-\alpha)} = 0 \pm s_{\text{cri}} \times \sigma_s$$

Where $\sigma_s = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{n\sqrt{n}} \sigma \sqrt{1-\rho_{\bar{y}_2\bar{y}_1}}$

$\rho_{\bar{y}_2\bar{y}_1}$ = The correlation between the two mean values.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, descriptive analysis is performed on sugarcane production across 19 Indian states from 1981 to 2022, including various statistical measures such as minimum, maximum, average, standard deviation (S.D.) and coefficient of variation (CV). The observed results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of sugarcane production (thousand tonnes)

State	Minimum	Maximum	Average	S.D.	CV
Andhra Pradesh & Telangana (APT)	5889.6	21692	13346.3	3733.221	27.972
Assam	871.2	2687.2	1356.2	431.146	31.791
Bihar	3729	20116.3	7552.9	4200.782	55.618
Gujarat	5022.8	17459.1	11622.2	3054.985	26.286
Haryana	5130	10650	7475.7	1420.141	18.997
Himachal Pradesh	20.1	139.1	45	25.013	55.562
Karnataka	12820	61152	29031.7	11853.449	40.829
Kerala	10.4	916.5	371.1	214.251	57.737
Madhya Pradesh	1084	7433.8	2680.7	1657.799	61.843
Maharashtra	20475	123968.2	54216.6	27449.878	50.630
Meghalaya	0.2	9	1.8	2.391	134.071
Mizoram	0.8	51.3	14.2	16.334	114.967
Nagaland	30	247.3	142.4	55.144	38.731
Odisha	240.1	3700	1445.5	1104.998	76.444
Punjab	3700	11040	6517.6	1438.527	22.072

Rajasthan	276.6	1485.4	748.4	408.317	54.561
Tamil Nadu	13258	41124	25762.1	7805.925	30.300
Uttar Pradesh	70888.2	224245.9	121949.1	32993.072	27.055
West Bengal	542.4	2105.5	1337.6	415.502	31.063

The descriptive analysis gives important basic information about the sugarcane production. During the study period, Meghalaya state is recorded as the lowest production (0.2 thousand tonnes), followed by Mizoram (0.8 thousand tonnes). The minimum production across the states ranged from 0.2 thousand tonnes (Meghalaya) to 70,888.2 thousand tonnes (Uttar Pradesh). The state Uttar Pradesh is identified as the leading producer with 224,245.9 thousand tonnes, followed by Maharashtra with 1,23,968.2 thousand tonnes. Average production in thousand tonnes varies from 1.8 for the states of Meghalaya to 1,21,949.1 for Uttar Pradesh, respectively. The average production over multiple years provides a benchmark to compare whether a particular year's production is low or high.

It is necessary to observe the relative stability of the trend over time. The relative stability is detected by the coefficient of variation (CV). Here, production variability is categorized according to Yitea et al. (2021), where CV below 20% indicates low variability, between 20% and 30% represents medium variability, and above 30% signifies high variability. Most states exhibited high variability (i.e., $CV > 30\%$), with Haryana displaying the lowest variability (i.e., 18.997%). States such as Punjab, Gujarat, Uttar Pradesh, and APT fell within the medium variability range. The highest variability is recorded in Meghalaya, with a CV of 134.071%. This interpretation gives a glance at the spatial dispensaries of the sugarcane production of various states of India. But these facts are not enough to judge the actual trends of the sugarcane production. So, the ITA method is proposed, and the results are presented in Figures 1, 2 and 3 to study the production in detail.

Figure 1: Monotonic and nonmonotonic increasing trends

As per scatter plots from Figure 1, it is identified that eleven states have an increasing trend in sugarcane production. Among them, ten states exhibited a steady upward trajectory, while one state (Tamil Nadu) showed a nonmonotonic increasing trend. Over the period, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Nagaland, and Mizoram indicated strong and statistically significant growth, with their data points positioned well above the 5% line.

Additionally, Haryana, West Bengal, Gujarat, and Karnataka represented a moderate upward trend, with plotted values nearer to the 5% line. Bihar state initially did not represent any considerable trend but later changed into a statistically significant increasing trend over time.

Figure 2: Monotonic and nonmonotonic decreasing trends

Similarly, Figure 2 highlights five states, namely Assam, Kerala, Meghalaya, Odisha, and Rajasthan, are experiencing a consistent decline in sugarcane production. Himachal Pradesh has shown a nonmonotonic declining tendency, progressing over time from a negligible increase to a notable fall.

Figure 3 No trend

From Figure 3, Punjab and APT states are indicative of negligible nonmonotonic trends, in which there are rising and falling trends at various scales, even hidden ones within the same time series. These findings emphasize regional disparities in sugarcane production trends, underscoring the need for improved agricultural practices and sustainable resource management to enhance productivity in declining regions.

Moreover, the internal trend behaviours are detected in time series data by the segmentation of the 1:1line scatter method into three verbal clusters as low, medium, and high. Table 2 is constructed as per the results of Figures 1, 2 and 3, and it provides a detailed explanation of the trend classification based on "low", "medium", and "high". Here (+), (-) and (O) indicate the increasing, decreasing and no trend, while "YES" and "NO" indicate significant and insignificant at the 95% confidence level, respectively.

Plotting the scatter points on the graph allows for the analysis of the internal trend behaviour. Each and every state expressed their own structured trend patterns in sugarcane production. This comprehensive analysis is more realistic to understand the in-depth and hidden trends of sugarcane production. Table 2 data is classified and presented in simple graphic form (Figure 4).

Table 2: Trend classification of sugarcane production in India

State	Low	Medium	High	Explanation
APT	(-) YES	O	(+) YES	The low and high clusters exhibit slight decreasing and increasing trends, respectively, while the medium cluster does not display any significant trend pattern.
Assam	(-) YES	(-) YES	(-) YES	The production trend demonstrated a gradual decline across all three clusters. Initially, the decline is slight in the low cluster, followed by a moderate decrease in the medium cluster, and ultimately reaching its steepest level in the high cluster. This consistent downward trend across the clusters, therefore, serves as a clear warning signal for production in Assam.
Bihar	(+) YES	(+) YES	O	A positive trend is observed in both the low and medium clusters. Initially, there is a slight increase, which suddenly escalated to a high increasing trend in both clusters. No discernible trend at high cluster due to absence of data.
Gujarat	(+) YES	(+) YES	(+) YES	An increasing trend is detected across all three clusters. Notably, the highest increase is recorded in the low cluster. As the trend progressed to the medium cluster, it showed a slight fluctuation with a minor dip, but it rose again significantly in the high cluster.
Haryana	(+) YES	(+) YES	(+) YES	A moderate increasing trend is consistently observed across all three clusters, indicating a stable and steady growth pattern in the state.
Himachal Pradesh	O	(-) YES	(-) YES	The low cluster exhibited a trend-free pattern, with all data points lying within the threshold bands. However, as the analysis moved to the medium cluster, a slight decline is observed, which further steepened into a sharp decline in the high cluster.
Karnataka	(+) YES	(+) YES	(+) YES	The trend began with a slight to high increase in the low cluster. This is followed by a steep and very drastic upward trend in the medium and high clusters, respectively, showing significant growth.
Kerala	(-) YES	(-) YES	O	A strong declining trend is captured in both the low and medium clusters. However, data points are not identified in the high cluster, making it trend-free for that phase.

Madhya Pradesh	(+) YES	(+) YES	O	A steep increasing trend is evident in both the low and medium clusters. The scatter plot indicates a significantly rising growth rate from the low to the medium cluster. Due to the absence of data, no trend could be identified in the high cluster.
Maharashtra	(+) YES	(+) YES	(+) YES	A steep and continuous increasing trend is evident across all three clusters. The plotted points reflect a strong upward trajectory from low to medium to high clusters. This confirms that Maharashtra is one of the state continues to be a major contributor to sugarcane production over the years.
Meghalaya	O	(-) YES	(-) YES	No trend was observed in the low cluster. However, a sharp declining pattern emerged during the medium and high clusters, marking it as one of the worst performers in this period.
Mizoram	O	(+) YES	O	The low cluster displayed a trend-free nature, but the medium cluster showed a significantly increasing trend. The high cluster is trend-free due to a lack of data.
Nagaland	(+) YES	(+) YES	(+) YES	A consistently increasing trend is observed throughout all three clusters, indicating steady growth overtime.
Odisha	(-) YES	(-) YES	(-) YES	A downward trend is evident across all three clusters. While the low cluster reflected a slight decline, the medium and high clusters exhibited sharper declines, indicating worsening production.
Rajasthan	(-) YES	(-) YES	(-) YES	All three clusters showed a steep and continuous downward trend, pointing to a significant and persistent decline in production.
Uttar Pradesh	(+) YES	(+) YES	(+) YES	A sharp upward trend is captured in all three clusters. Notably, the trend gradually increases from one cluster to the next, suggesting that Uttar Pradesh holds a leading position than the other states.
West Bengal	(+) YES	(+) YES	O	The low and medium clusters show a continuous rising trend, whereas the high cluster shows no discernible trend.
Tamil Nadu	O	(+) YES	(+) YES	There is no trend in the low cluster, while the medium cluster follows a nonmonotonic rising trend, and the high cluster follows a slight rising trend.
Punjab	O	O	O	An insignificant nonmonotonic decline trend is observed in all three clusters.

Figure 4: Trend change % as per clusters

From Table 2 and Figure 4, it is noticed that the medium cluster is mainly dominated by rising trends (58%) rather than low (47%) and high (42%) clusters. It indicates that most of the state's productions are on an upward trend in the medium group. The medium cluster shows the highest proportion of declining trends (32%), whereas the low and high clusters each show a 26% share. In the case of no trend, the high cluster takes the major portion (32%), followed by the low (26%) and medium (11%).

Table 3: ITA slope results of sugarcane production

S. NO.	State	Slope (S)	Control Limit(95%)		Sig.	Nature
			Lower	Upper		
1	APT	-4.79	-13.51	13.51	NO	↓
2	Assam	-27.87	-1.69	1.69	YES	↓
3	Bihar	236.92	-26.86	26.86	YES	↑
4	Gujarat	192.96	-12.11	12.11	YES	↑
5	Haryana	48.39	-5.97	5.97	YES	↑
6	Himachal Pradesh	-0.6	-0.15	0.15	YES	↓
7	Karnataka	525.62	-51.26	51.26	YES	↑
8	Kerala	-13.1	-1.34	1.34	YES	↓
9	Madhya Pradesh	110.47	-8.11	8.11	YES	↑
10	Maharashtra	1786.58	-150.45	150.45	YES	↑
11	Meghalaya	-0.14	-0.02	0.02	YES	↓
12	Mizoram	0.84	-0.11	0.11	YES	↑
13	Nagaland	3.21	-0.23	0.23	YES	↑
14	Odisha	-70.97	-3.75	3.75	YES	↓
15	Punjab	-6.4	-9.39	9.39	NO	↓
16	Rajasthan	-32.09	-2.63	2.63	YES	↓
17	Tamil Nadu	37.93	-30.01	30.01	YES	↑
18	Uttar Pradesh	2063.01	-222.14	222.14	YES	↑
19	West Bengal	12.53	-1.68	1.68	YES	↑

The results of the ITA method offer detailed insights about regional patterns, effectively capturing the direction, intensity, and statistical significance of trends across Indian states. The trend slope quantifies the average rate of change over time, with a positive sign indicating growth rate and a negative sign signalling a decline rate in production. As per Table 3, the ITA slope analysis revealed that 17 out of 19 (89%) of the majority of the states had a statistically significant change in trends of sugarcane production over the period 1981–2022. Among them, 11 (65%) states experienced an upward trend, while 6 (35%) states showed a decline. The remaining 2 states, APT and Punjab, have not shown any significant trend at the 5% level of significance.

As per the magnitude of the trend slope, Uttar Pradesh is highlighted as having the most notable increase trend, with the highest average growth rate of change being 2,063.01 thousand tonnes/year, followed by Maharashtra at 1,786.58 thousand tonnes/year, while Karnataka recorded an increase of 525.62 thousand tonnes/year in sugarcane production. Furthermore, the steepest average decline is identified in Odisha, with the highest average decline rate of -70.97 thousand tonnes/year, followed by Rajasthan (-32.09 thousand tonnes/year) and Assam (-27.87 thousand tonnes/year). The average rate of change in sugarcane production varies from a decline of -70.97 thousand tonnes/year in Odisha to an increase of 2063.01 thousand tonnes/year in Uttar Pradesh.

The results of the ITA method, highlighting the direction, strength, and significant nature of trends, give an in-depth understanding of the regional patterns in every state in India. The overall study provided valuable insights about sugarcane production trends, offering a clearer understanding of how the states are involved in the contribution of the sugarcane production as well as its possibility to determine whether future demand can be met or not. States with increasing production should prioritise technological advancements and sustainable practices, while those experiencing declines require improved irrigation, soil conservation, and policy support to restore productivity. Addressing these disparities will be crucial for ensuring a stable supply and the long-term sustainability of sugarcane production in India.

4. CONCLUSION

A new statistical trend analysis was performed on sugarcane production over four decades in 19 Indian states and evaluated important insights about various regions. Based on the ITA graph method, 17 states exhibited significant trends. Among them, 14 states showed monotonic trends, while 3 states displayed nonmonotonic patterns. Specifically, 11 states experienced significant growth, and the remaining states showed declining trends. There was

no trend observed in APT or Punjab. In addition to that, the increasing trends were slightly dominating the decreasing trends in all three clusters. Even while a sizable percentage (32%) of states in the medium cluster were experiencing decline, there was still a slight overall edge towards growth.

The ITA slope results highlighted that states like Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Karnataka were leading producers of sugarcane. The steepest declining trends were observed in Odisha, Rajasthan, and Assam. This suggests that these states may be encountering challenges that are adversely affecting their sugarcane output. To solve this issue, the government and farmers must adopt legislative measures and better farming practices. Such actions will help reduce the gap between demand and supply while also promoting the sustainability and growth of sugarcane cultivation in India.

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